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FROM SILOS TO SYSTEMS: ENABLING OFF-GRID ELECTRIFICATION OF HEALTHCARE FACILITIES, HOUSEHOLDS AND BUSINESSES IN SUB-SAHARAN AFRICA

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SUMMARY

Electrification gaps greatly impede healthcare service provision in sub-Saharan Africa. In a recent *Joule* article, Moner-Girona et al. show that electrifying unconnected healthcare facilities with solar off-grid systems is feasible and cost-effective. Here, I discuss critical design, operations and enabling environment characteristics to implement integrated off-grid solutions for sustainable development at scale.

The UN has defined Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 7 to underline its aim to provide access to sustainable, reliable and modern energy to all by 2030. Currently, roughly 600 million people in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) have no access to electricity¹. While energy access issues are most commonly discussed in terms of lacking household electrification, they can have dramatic consequences for healthcare facilities that are unable to provide basic medical services such as safely storing medicines and vaccines, power an incubator for premature babies or even ensuring proper lighting while medical procedures are performed.

In their insightful recent article, Moner-Girona et al.² use sophisticated and remarkably encompassing geospatial analyses to identify a considerable electricity access gap of healthcare facilities in Africa. Of the roughly 123,000 facilities they map, they identify approximately 57,000 to have no electricity access. They then estimate the size and cost of location-specific solar-powered off-grid energy systems needed to electrify these facilities, finding average levelised cost of roughly 0.4 USD/kWh, and a comparably low cost of 484 million USD to achieve electrification of all African health centres. In addition to system component costs (PV cells, batteries, control unit, wiring),

these figures critically also include project development costs for system design, project management, training, licensing and installation which are often overlooked.

With Moner-Girona et al.'s² contribution suggesting its feasibility, the urgent question that remains is how this promising, cost-efficient and environmentally friendly solution can best be designed and implemented to maximise sustainable development (SD) benefits at scale. I believe there are three critical components, namely (1) systems-wide off-grid energy solution design approaches, (2) optimised operations strategy building on Artificial intelligence (AI) methods, and (3) an adequate enabling environment (Figure 1). The remainder of this paper addresses these three components in turn.

Note: First, explicitly designing off-grid systems for multiple SDG benefits, including investment decisions for appliances, captures synergies across SDGs. Second, AI approaches help to ensure optimal operations in the short- and long-term. Third, implementation of off-grid systems targeted at multiple SDGs requires new business models, cross-sectoral governance and tailored finance to create an enabling environment.

Figure 1: Three key components of designing and implementing integrated off-grid energy systems at scale.

System-wide off-grid energy solution design

Moner-Girona et al.'s solution hints at existing synergies between SDG7 (energy access) and SDG3 (good health)². However, their paper does not yet explicitly analyse the energy access challenge for households, healthcare facilities and businesses in a joint fashion. The cost to design and implement projects for SD in rural Africa can be up to 30 – 40% of overall project cost³. Hence, integrating multiple energy-related SD projects into one, with the resulting energy system capable of simultaneously delivering on multiple SDGs, can realise significant cost synergies. Critically, this logic holds true beyond SDG3 and SDG7: indeed, a majority of the SDGs' 169 targets have a strong link to energy access^{4,5}, including reducing poverty (SDG 1.1), doubling agricultural productivity (SDG 2.3), upgrading education facilities (SDG 4.a), providing access to clean water (SDG 6.1), increasing the value-add of labour (SDG 8.2), and reducing food waste (SDG 12.3). Cost synergies from project integration in a given location can be expected to monotonously increase the more SDGs are tackled simultaneously versus each being addressed in a silo. There is thus considerable merit in building on Moner-Girona et al.'s² idea towards adopting a systems perspective when designing off-grid energy systems in SSA.

Furthermore, access to electricity alone does not contribute to socio-economic development. To ensure impact for SDG3, as well as any other SDG outside of SDG 7, it is key to include decisions on which type of appliances are required at the energy system planning stage. In their important study, Lenz et al. find that specifically in health centres, appliance uptake is very low even years after electrification in East Africa⁶. This is despite the fact that appliances such as freezers, incubators, sterilisers, microscopes, spectrophotometers, computers and lighting are usually one to two orders of magnitude cheaper than the energy system-related investment costs. Hence, considering appliances and their cost is key for planning off-grid energy systems to fully reap the potential benefits of health centre, and similarly household and small-scale business electrification.

Intelligent operations

Optimising operations is critical for solar energy-based off-grid systems. To minimise lifetime cost, maximise reliability and reduce the production of toxic waste, Big Data and AI smart grid approaches are key in achieving operational excellence of off-grid systems in the short- as well as the medium/long-term. For short-term operational excellence, being able to deal with the intermittence of solar energy supply and system demand is key. AI approaches can accurately predict electricity generation and demand dynamics to help identify the optimal electricity dispatch strategy. Batteries are crucial in this regard. They account for roughly 20% of initial system costs^{3,7}, and need to be replaced after 3 – 6 years as their capacity slightly decreases with every charge and discharge cycle. Managing battery charge and discharge speed and depth, optimal dispatch

strategies optimise for the most battery-friendly system operation while meeting demand. Remote monitoring and control systems such as the one implemented by solar off-grid company BBOXX enable this approach by collecting time-specific appliance, generation and demand data and sending it to an online server where the analyses can be performed⁷.

Aimed at medium-term operations management, machine learning-based models using such historical data can predict when solar PV cells need to be cleaned, and when batteries will start to fail, ensuring that they are replaced before a healthcare facility is left without reliable electricity supply⁷. Longer-term, while more research is needed in this field, AI-based systems appear to have the potential to help integrate mini-grid systems into the national grid when the latter arrives in the area.

Adequate enabling environment

Building on a recent framework by Khosla et al. for accelerating a sustainability transition in a sector where access is a critical issue⁸, I see three main enablers to achieve such integrated solutions, namely (i) integrated business models, (ii) cross-sectoral policies and governance, and (iii) financing integrated solutions.

Integrated business models. The private sector is widely viewed as being fundamental for helping to bridge SD gaps in Africa⁹. To deliver on integrated solutions at scale, business model innovations are required that simultaneously capture economic, social and environmental value. Currently, in addition to grant finance, most mini-grid developers in Africa aim to recover their costs by charging customers per kWh consumed¹⁰. Most recent solar mini-grid designs would amortise if domestic consumers paid roughly 0.6 – 0.8 USD/kWh (slightly higher compared to Moner-Girona et al.'s² finding for healthcare facilities due to additional distribution grid and project development costs). These numbers, however, are almost quadruple of the average national tariff in SSA. In response, innovative African mini-grid companies have started to invest in appliances to be able to offer different end-user services on top of merely providing energy access. This approach can drive impact across SDGs and increase company profitability: The appliances they buy and run create energy-enabled productivity gains in rural supply chains which can be monetised directly. For instance, producing ice to avoid food loss or incubating chicken eggs can return 1 USD in economic value created per kWh generated¹¹. This resulting higher value-add per kWh yields additional commercial revenue streams, which can cross-subsidise non-commercial electricity demand such as household use and healthcare facilities to unlock electricity uptake.

Cross-sectoral policies and governance. Fostering sector integration such as energy and health requires a careful policy balancing act. On the one hand, policy makers need to put in place overarching policy strategies and concrete regulatory instruments that build a long-term foundation and draws actors into the space of integrated energy-enabled solutions. On the other hand, they also need to implement regulations that ensure that implementing organisations adhere to the defined development objectives, including equity and justice principles. This balancing act requires negotiation across a variety of case-specific ministries. A key first step tends to be the creation of specific forums for such cross-sectoral policy making where these structures do not yet exist. Benin is an insightful case in this regard: The country has implemented a cross-sectoral governance organ called the *Ministère du cadre de vie et du développement durable* (Ministry of the Living Environment and Sustainable Development) which combines cross-ministerial expertise to incorporate broad sustainability principles into government decision making and benefit from capturing cross-sectoral SD synergies.

Financing integrated solutions. A lack of finance is a key reason why so many African healthcare facilities remain unelectrified, and a key barrier for solutions such as proposed by Moner-Girona et al.² to be implemented at scale. Paradoxically, despite the cross-cutting nature of SD and deep interlinkages between different SDGs, there is an alarming paucity of finance instruments specifically tailored towards funding solutions which address multiple SDGs simultaneously (such as healthcare and household energy access). Indeed, most available large-scale performance-based off-grid energy development finance grants for instance solely focus on achieving SDG 7, at the expense of its potential wider systemic impact: Mini-grid companies can get a grant from the World Bank for connecting a household or health centre, but find it difficult to get funding for appliances which do not count towards SDG 7 but are key to achieve energy-related impact in all other SDGs. Innovative African startups such as EnerGrow in Uganda are stepping into this void and explicitly provide appliance finance. Given the need to incentivise appliance uptake⁵, supporting such schemes and implementing them at scale using government and development finance appears to be a low-cost and high-return way of de-risking integrated SD solutions and capitalising on the potential of energy access for healthcare facilities, and for SD at large.

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